

Critical Aspects of Quality Management in Flexible Pavement Construction

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Abstract

The presence of a reliable road network plays a significant role in the economic growth of any country. Roads are a key factor in the economic development of a nation, facilitating the movement of people and goods. A reliable road network ensures smooth and safe transportation, promoting efficiency in trade and commerce. In contrast, the absence of such infrastructure can delay and hinder the movement of goods, severely impacting economic progress. Global spending on infrastructure projects is projected to increase from approximately \$4 trillion per year in 2012 to nearly \$9 trillion per year by 2025. This significant rise in investment highlights the critical importance of infrastructure, including road networks, in supporting economic growth.

The construction of roads involves various stages before, during, and after the construction process. Poor quality assurance (QA) and quality control (QC) measures during any stage can result in low-quality roads incapable of sustaining expected traffic loads. Such roads are prone to damage and deterioration under regular usage. Therefore, implementing effective QA/QC procedures and control measures during road construction is essential. Proper application of QA/QC protocols ensures the construction of reliable and durable roads capable of performing efficiently throughout their design life. Additionally, well-constructed roads reduce the long-term costs associated with maintenance and rehabilitation.

Key words: pavement, quality, asphalt, marshal, bitumen, density.

1. Introduction

Quality is simply the fulfillment of customers' needs and the meeting of their expectations [12]. Producing a quality road that meets specifications requires the implementation of a stringent quality management system. Implementing strict QA/QC procedures and control measures during the construction stage alone is not sufficient to ensure the durability and performance of roads. QA/QC procedures must be applied during the design, construction, and testing phases of road pavement projects. Using correct construction methods alone is not enough to produce high-quality pavements. Therefore, every aspect of pavement construction must be addressed with the utmost care. The implementation of QA/QC procedures should be thorough and encompass all aspects of pavement construction. Partial failure in implementing QA/QC procedures can seriously

affect the quality and performance of the pavement.

Flexible pavement is widely used worldwide and dominates the road construction industry. Approximately 95% of the roads in the world are made of flexible pavement [20]. The dominance of flexible pavement can be attributed to its lower initial cost compared to rigid pavement. Additionally, the maintenance and upgrading of flexible pavement are easier than for rigid pavement [15].

This paper will briefly discuss the various factors that can impact the quality and durability of flexible pavement:

- Existing ground conditions: The impact of ground conditions on pavement performance.
- Weather conditions: Weather can significantly affect flexible pavement, reducing its durability and service life.

- Traffic loads: Improper estimation of traffic loads can shorten the service life of flexible pavement, leading to premature defects.
- Materials testing: Testing pavement materials is crucial to ensure that the quality of materials complies with specifications and minimum requirements.
- Construction of flexible pavement: Constructing flexible pavement involves handling various materials, such as granular and asphalt materials. Proper laying and compaction of these materials, according to correct procedures, are essential. Any deviation can result in poor pavement quality.

2. Flexible pavement

Flexible pavement is a layered structure that deflects under traffic loads. It is composed of layers of granular materials and asphalt. High-quality materials with the highest bearing capacity, such as asphaltic concrete layers, are placed at the top of the flexible pavement as they are exposed to the highest levels of stress [26]. The thickness and number of layers are not fixed and depend on various parameters, including the type of road, traffic volume, design life, subgrade condition, and more.

The structural design of flexible pavement requires an accurate estimation of traffic loads over its design life. A precise estimation of traffic loads ensures a properly designed pavement structure capable of sustaining the expected stresses. However, correct structural design must be integrated with a thorough study of subgrade conditions, strict quality control of pavement materials, and the application of proper construction methods.

3.0 Factor impacting quality of pavement

There are numerous reasons that can cause the failure of newly constructed roads. A

comprehensive study of the existing site conditions and traffic condition is essential to develop a precise structural design for the pavement that can withstand expected traffic loads.

3.1 Pavement subgrade

The subgrade is the natural soil layer beneath the pavement structure. Traffic loads carried by the pavement are transferred to the subgrade. Therefore, the subgrade must have sufficient strength and stiffness to carry these loads without excessive deformation. The physical properties of the subgrade, or the soil beneath the pavement, should be thoroughly tested and analyzed to confirm its suitability [11]. Subgrade evaluation typically involves various tests, including the plasticity index, liquid limit, sieve analysis, percentage of organic material, California Bearing Ratio (CBR), etc [11].

The AASHTO soil classification system categorizes soil into groups A-1 through A-7 based on parameters such as the plasticity index, liquid limit, and sieve analysis. Table No. 01 presents the different soil groups according to the AASHTO classification, along with a general rating of each soil group's suitability as a pavement subgrade. It can be observed that the increase in fine material percentage, liquid limit, and plasticity index negatively affects soil strength and reduces its suitability as a subgrade material.

It is essential to collect sufficient soil samples from the existing site before beginning pavement construction to conduct necessary tests, verify the soil's physical properties, and classify it according to the AASHTO classification system. Generally, suitable soil groups for subgrades include A-1, A-3, A-2-4, and A-2-5 when properly drained and compacted [25].

Table 1

General Classification	Granular Materials (35 % or less passing No. 200)							Silt-Clay Materials (More than 35 % passing No. 200)			
	A-1		A-3	A-2				A-4	A-5	A-6	A-7
Group classification	A-1-a	A-1-b		A-2-4	A-2-5	A-2-6	A-2-7				
Sieve analysis, % passing:											
No. 10 (2.00 mm)	50 max
No. 40 (425 µm)	30 max	50 max	51 min
No. 200 (75 µm)	15 max	25 max	10 max	35 max	35 max	35 max	35 max	36 min	36 min	36 min	36 min
Characteristics of fraction passing No. 40 (425 µm):											
Liquid limit	40 max 10 max	41 min 10 max	40 max 11 min	41 min 11 min	40 max 10 max	41 min 10 max	40 max 11 min	41 min 11 min
Plasticity index	6 max	...	N.P.	Silty or Clayey Gravel and Sand				Silty Soils		Clayey Soils	
Usual types of significant constituent materials	Stone Fragments, Gravel and Sand		Fine Sand								
General rating as subgrade	Excellent to Good							Fair to Poor			

Additionally, the Group Index (GI) can be used according to AASHTO classification system to further evaluate soil suitability and relative performance as a subgrade material [11]. The Group Index is calculated using the following formula:

$$GI=0.2(F-35)+0.005(F-35)(LL-40)+0.01(F-15)(PI-10)$$

Where:

F is the percentage passing through sieve no: 200

PI is the plasticity index

LL is the liquid limit

Table No. 02 evaluates soil performance as a subgrade material based on the Group Index. Lower Group Index values indicate better performance as a subgrade. Soils with lower Group Index values also tend to exhibit non-expansive properties and improved drainage characteristics.

Table 2 [11]

Type of subgrade soil	Group index range of subgrade
Good	0 – 1
Fair	2 – 4
Poor	5 – 9
Very poor	10 – 20

In addition to testing physical properties, engineers may need to investigate the presence of cavities beneath the proposed pavement. Undetected cavities can compromise the structural capacity of the road, leading to excessive settlement or even collapse. Various methods, such as probe drilling, ground-penetrating radar, and electrical resistivity surveys, can be employed to detect underground cavities. Untreated cavities beneath the pavement can result in road collapse, as illustrated in Figure No. 01. Detected cavities should be treated with grouting or other suitable methods.

Figure 1

A poor subgrade cannot effectively support traffic loads. It will deflect excessively under

these loads, leading to serious pavement defects such as structural cracks, rutting, and settlement [21]. Therefore, thorough testing of the existing soil is crucial to avoid undesirable consequences and to ensure a durable pavement.

The placement of pavement on poor subgrade soil should be avoided. If necessary, engineers may propose replacing a specific thickness of the existing soil with an improved subgrade. Enhancing the subgrade beneath the proposed pavement increases its strength and stiffness, significantly reducing pavement deflection and settlement.

3.2 The impact of climate

Flexible pavement is an exposed and unprotected structure that can be directly affected by climate change. Harsh environmental conditions can adversely impact the pavement's performance and service life. The interaction between pavement and the environment can lead to various types of distress. In general, temperature, precipitation, and groundwater directly influence the performance of flexible pavement. Engineers should consider prevailing climate conditions during the design and construction stages to mitigate any adverse impacts caused by these factors.

3.2.1 Temperature impact on flexible pavement

It is important to consider the prevailing temperature's impact on pavement during the design stage of a pavement structure. Temperature can significantly affect flexible pavement, reducing its performance and bearing capacity. Extreme high and low temperatures have adverse effects on pavement structures, primarily impacting the asphalt layers.

The properties of the bitumen binder in asphalt layers are highly sensitive to temperature. Variations in temperature beyond a certain limit alter the bitumen binder's properties, affecting the stress-strain response and load distribution of the pavement [27]. High temperatures can cause

the binder to soften and lose stiffness, leading to excessive pavement deformation under loads. Conversely, low temperatures increase the stiffness of asphalt layers, reducing the pavement's flexibility. Low temperatures can also generate thermal tensile stresses that exceed the asphalt layer's tensile strength, inducing thermal cracking [19].

Modern pavement design methods, such as the mechanistic-empirical design method, require detailed climatic data to predict pavement distress accurately [18]. This approach emphasizes the significant impact of climate on constructed roads and the need for climate-adaptive design strategies.

Various measures can be implemented by engineers to minimize the adverse effects of temperature:

- **Use of Polymer-Modified Bitumen (PMP):**
Incorporating PMP in asphalt mixtures improves durability, increases service life, and reduces pavement maintenance. Various grades of PMP, such as PG82-22, perform well within a temperature range of 82°C to -22°C [13]. The use of PMP significantly mitigates the negative impact of temperature on flexible pavement, providing better resistance to rutting and cracking.
- **Adjusting Bitumen Content:**
Reducing bitumen content near to lower limits can improve pavement performance at high temperatures by decreasing its temperature sensitivity. For example, the ideal bitumen content for base and wearing courses in the UK ranges from 4% to 4.7%, while in the UAE, it ranges from 3.2% to 4.4%. Increasing bitumen content in hot climates can lead to asphalt bleeding and excessive stiffness in the asphalt mixture.

- **Other Measures:**

Additional strategies can be used to reduce the impact of temperature on flexible pavement include increasing pavement thickness and using fiber-reinforced asphalt to enhance resistance to temperature-related stresses.

Considering climate impacts during the design stage is essential to reduce pavement distress. Temperature variations can adversely affect pavement performance, causing issues such as cracking, rutting, and premature aging. Therefore, engineers must account for prevailing climatic conditions to mitigate or eliminate the impact of temperature on pavement structures effectively.

3.2.2 Precipitation and ground impact on flexible pavement

Precipitation and groundwater have a negative impact on flexible pavement. Both precipitation and groundwater increase the moisture levels within the pavement, which can lead to significant damage. Heavy rainfall without proper drainage results in water accumulation, forming ponds on the pavement surface. The accumulated water can seep into the pavement through cracks, propagating them and accelerating pavement deterioration.

Moreover, surface runoff significantly increases the moisture levels in the layers beneath the pavement. Excessive moisture in the subgrade and pavement layers greatly reduces the resilient modulus and bearing capacity of the pavement. High moisture levels also decrease the shear resistance of the subgrade and pavement layers, diminishing the pavement's ability to resist permanent deformation or rutting. Under extreme conditions, such as heavy rainfall or flooding, pavement collapse may occur.

Providing an efficient drainage system is essential to channel water away from the pavement and prevent water accumulation. Proper drainage significantly reduces the negative impact of heavy rainfall on pavement

performance. Additionally, designers should consider and investigate the groundwater table during the design stage. Increasing the clearance between the groundwater table and the pavement structure can further reduce moisture-related damage.

3.3 Estimation of traffic load

Failure to accurately estimate traffic loads can result in a deficient pavement incapable of supporting the expected traffic loads. The primary factor for accurate estimation of traffic loads is conducting a thorough traffic survey. Traffic on pavements comprises a mixture of vehicles with varying axle loads and configurations, such as single-axle, tandem-axle, and tridem-axle setups. Heavy vehicles cause significantly more damage to pavement structures compared to smaller vehicles.

Therefore, a classified vehicle count, combined with an axle load survey, is crucial for estimating the percentage of heavy vehicles within the total traffic volume and determining axle loads and configurations for different vehicle types. The AASHTO 1993 design method utilizes the concept of Equivalent Single Axle Load (ESAL). ESAL converts all traffic loads into an equivalent single-axle load with standard axle load [26]. Accurate determination of ESAL requires detailed traffic and axle load surveys to measure factors such as average daily traffic, the percentage of trucks, axle loads, configurations and others. In contrast, the Mechanistic-Empirical Pavement Design Method (MEPDG) has abandoned the ESAL concept. Instead, MEPDG requires determining the full axle load spectrum for different vehicles, which necessitates a detailed axle load survey [18].

In summary, regardless of the design method adopted, the design of pavement structures is heavily influenced by traffic load estimation. Accurate estimation is essential to designing a pavement with sufficient capacity to withstand traffic loads throughout its design life.

3.4 Pavement materials

Flexible pavement structures are composed of several layers, typically including granular layers and asphalt layers. Granular layers are placed above the subgrade and beneath the asphalt layers to enhance the pavement's bearing capacity and support traffic loads without excessive deformation. Various granular materials are used in pavement construction such as subbase and aggregate road base being the most common.

In flexible pavement, asphalt layers are placed above the granular materials. The number and thickness of asphalt layers depend on the anticipated traffic loads and the type of road. Flexible pavement structures may include multiple asphaltic courses, such as the base course, binder course, and wearing course, each serving specific purposes within the pavement system.

Ensuring the quality of flexible pavement materials is critical for constructing durable pavement that meets requirements and expectations. Quality control is achieved through various QA/QC measures, including testing the properties of received materials to confirm compliance with specified requirements and standards [12].

3.4.1 Granular materials

Granular material is a mixture of crushed or natural coarse and fine aggregates. These aggregates must be hard and durable to sustain traffic loads without crushing. Subbase and aggregate base course materials are commonly used in flexible pavements. In general, aggregate base courses possess higher bearing capacity and

better quality compared to subbase materials [16]. Granular materials are widely used in flexible pavements to enhance pavement properties and structural capacity.

Since the bearing capacity of existing subgrades is often low, subbase and aggregate base course layers are added to reduce the traffic stresses transferred to the subgrade to acceptable levels. Verifying the quality of granular materials is essential for producing durable roads. Engineers should implement various QA/QC procedures to ensure the quality of granular materials.

The source of materials delivered to the site must be verified by the Engineer. Before procurement, samples of granular materials should be collected and tested for compliance with specifications and standards. Periodic sample collection and testing during construction confirm the quality of delivered materials. Testing frequency is specified in project specifications and is vital for detecting deviations and enabling swift corrective actions. Furthermore, the Engineer must ensure that materials are tested in credible, independent, and qualified laboratories.

Common quality tests for Granular Material:

- **Gradation:** Gradation can be defined as the particle size distribution in granular material. The gradation test will be conducted using a set of sieves, each with a different opening size. The material will be sieved through these sieves, and the amount retained or passed on each sieve will be determined from the total specimen.

Table 3

Sieve Designation		Mass Percent Passing					
Standard, mm	Alternate	Grading A	Grading B	Grading C	Grading D	Grading E	Grading F
50.0	2 in.	100	100	—	—	—	—
25.0	1 in.	—	75–95	100	100	100	100
9.5	3/8 in.	30–65	40–75	50–85	60–100	—	—
4.75	No. 4	25–55	30–60	35–65	50–85	55–100	70–100
2.00	No. 10	15–40	20–45	25–50	40–70	40–100	55–100
0.425	No. 40	8–20	15–30	15–30	25–45	20–50	30–70
0.075	No. 200	2–8	5–20	5–15	5–20	6–20	8–25

The material sample will then be divided according to particle size, representing the actual granular material gradation. Material retained on sieve No. 4 (4.75 mm) is classified as coarse aggregate, while material passing sieve No. 4 is considered fine material. Table No. 03 provides typical gradation for aggregate base course and subbase according to AASHTO M-147. Different countries may specify different gradations based on their past experience, local conditions, and available resources.

Gradation influences compaction, density, strength, and stability of granular material. Subbase and aggregate base courses should be well-graded, as it enhances compaction and results in a dense and stable material. Therefore, the engineer should ensure that the material's gradation complies with the standard and project specifications. Furthermore, the granular material should be properly mixed before laying and compaction.

- **Los Angeles Abrasion:** The Los Angeles Abrasion test is used to assess the quality of aggregates and their resistance to impact and abrasive forces [4]. The test utilizes a rotating drum with steel spheres to generate impact and abrasion forces. The drum will rotate for a specified number of

revolutions (500 revolutions as per AASHTO T-96), after which the aggregates will be sieved to measure the percentage of degradation. This test provides an important indication of the aggregate's hardness. As the quality of aggregates decreases, they will yield a greater amount of fines when tested.

- **Soundness:** The soundness test is used mainly to assess the resistance of aggregates to weathering action [1]. Aggregates are sieved, and the weight of each size is recorded to determine the amount of loss after the test. The test is conducted by immersing aggregates in a saturated solution of magnesium or sodium sulfate for a period of 16-18 hours, then oven-drying the aggregates. The process is repeated for 5 cycles [17]. The immersion and drying in the saturated solution simulate internal expansive forces that mimic freezing-thawing actions. Upon completion, the aggregates are sieved using the same sieves as initially used, and the amount of loss in each sieve and the total loss are determined.
- **California Bearing Ratio (CBR):** The CBR test evaluates the strength and bearing capacity of granular materials [24]. Additionally, the CBR value is used in the design of pavement structures. A higher CBR value indicates higher strength and bearing capacity, which plays a significant role

in determining pavement layer thickness. CBR represents the ratio of the loads required to penetrate a soil sample by 2.5 or 5 cm to the loads required to penetrate a standard soil sample. The CBR value is calculated using the following equation:

$$CBR = \frac{\text{corrected load value}}{\text{standard load value}} * 100\%$$

Figure 2

In general, CBR at 2.5 cm penetration will be higher than CBR at 5.0 cm penetration. However, if the CBR at 5 cm is greater than at 2.5 cm, the test should be repeated. If the retest yields the same result, the CBR at 5 cm should be used [24].

- Liquid Limit and Plasticity Index:** Atterberg limits, or liquid limit and plasticity index, are measured for material passing sieve 0.425 mm in subbase and aggregate base course [3]. The liquid limit is defined as the minimum water content at which soil transitions from a plastic state to a liquid state, while the plasticity index is the difference between the liquid limit and plastic limit [3]. Determining these parameters is crucial to controlling the quality of fines in granular materials.

High liquid limit and plasticity index indicate the presence of high-plasticity and compressible soils, such as clay. Clay materials exhibit undesirable swelling and shrinkage properties. Furthermore, they undergo a high reduction in volume under loads. Therefore, determining the liquid limit and plasticity index is important for ensuring the suitability of material for pavement construction.

- Flakiness and Elongation of Aggregates:** The flakiness and elongation index are used to assess the impact of aggregate shape on the strength and suitability of granular materials. Aggregates with a largest dimension greater than 1.80 times the mean dimension are considered elongated. Flaky aggregates are those with a least dimension less than 0.60 of the mean dimension. The excessive presence of flaky and elongated aggregates in subbase and aggregate base course will reduce the strength and stability of the granular materials.
- Sand Equivalency Test:** The sand equivalency test is conducted to measure the proportions of clay-size or plastic fines and dust in granular soil and fine aggregates [7]. The test is performed by adding a flocculating solution to a graduated cylinder containing a pre-measured soil sample. The solution is agitated to separate the clay particles, dust, and plastic fines from the fine aggregates. Additional flocculating solution is added to force the clay particles into suspension, and the sand is allowed to settle. The height of the sedimented sand is measured, and the sand equivalency is calculated using the formula:

$$\text{sand equivalency} = \frac{\text{sand reading}}{\text{clay reading}} * 100\%$$

Low sand equivalency indicates a high proportion of clay-like particles in the soil or fine aggregates. An increase in sand equivalency reflects better quality and fewer contaminants in the material.

- Maximum Dry Density and OMC:** in this test dry density is determined for a set of moisture content to determine the optimum moisture content (OMC) and the corresponding maximum dry density [22]. The relationship between dry density and moisture content is represented in a graph, similar to Figure No. 3. MDD and OMC are determined simply from this graph. This test is critical for determining the correct amount of mixing water needed for granular materials to achieve the maximum degree of compaction in the field.

Figure 3

- Organic Matter Content:** High organic content can impair the suitability of the pavement layer and lead to various defects. It increases the compressibility of subbase and aggregate base course, resulting in pavement settlement under load [10]. Organic matter will decompose over time, creating voids and causing pavement settlement. Organic content is determined by the loss on ignition method. In this method, a weighted soil sample is placed in an oven for 6 hours. Afterward, the sample is weighed to determine the organic

content [23]. The organic content is calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Percent of organic content} = \frac{A - B}{A - C} * 100$$

Where

A = mass of crucible or evaporating dish and oven-dried soil, before ignition;

B = mass of crucible or evaporating dish and oven-dried soil, after ignition;

C = mass of crucible or evaporating dish, to the nearest 0.01 g.

Periodic testing to verify the properties of granular materials is crucial for controlling the quality of pavement. The engineer should ensure that the tested materials comply with standards and specifications. Specifications generally outline material requirements and testing frequencies. Table No. 04 provides the requirements for subbase and aggregate base course materials, along with testing frequencies. Materials used in pavement construction must meet project specifications. It is important to note that the requirement will vary for different countries. In case of any deviation, immediate action should be taken, such as conducting additional tests or changing material sources.

Table 4

Test	Limit (Subbase)	Limit (Base course)	Frequency
Los angles abrasion	≤30%	≤30%	Every 3000 m3
Soundness (5 cycle)	≤15%	≤12%	
CBR	≥30	≥80	
Liquid limit	≤35%	≤35%	
PI	≤6	≤6	
Flakiness index	-	≤35%	
Elongation	-	≤35%	
Sand equivalency	≥35%	≥40%	
Organic content	≤0.20%	≤0.20%	

3.4.2 Asphaltic concrete

Hot mix asphalt (HMA) consists of aggregates and asphalt binder mixed together at high temperatures and used as a paving material. There are different types of HMA, such as dense-graded mixes, stone-matrix asphalt mixes, and open-graded asphalt mixtures [2]. Each of these mixtures has unique properties.

Dense-graded asphalt mixtures are widely used and suitable for all types of pavements and traffic conditions [2]. Every asphalt mixture should be carefully designed to determine the appropriate proportions of materials that meet the required standards and specifications. There are three common design methods: Marshall, Hveem, and Superpave. The Marshall method is particularly common and widely used worldwide.

A rigorous procedure must be followed to produce a high-quality asphalt mix that satisfies specifications and ensures durable pavement. The materials used to produce asphalt mixes, such as aggregates and bitumen binder, must be thoroughly tested to verify their quality and compliance with relevant standards and requirements. Furthermore, The Marshall method will be employed to design the mix, determine the optimum bitumen content, and ensure that the stability and voids requirements are met.

3.4.2.1 Aggregates for asphalt mix

The properties of aggregates significantly influence the characteristics of asphalt mixtures. The appropriate selection of aggregate sources and periodic testing are essential to ensure a high-quality asphalt mix that can withstand traffic loads with minimal defects. Aggregates should be produced from hard, tough, and durable stones. Producing aggregates by crushing is recommended, as it improves their shape, angularity, and internal friction, while also enhancing the pavement's resistance to deformation and rutting. It is important to note

that rounded aggregates possess low internal friction, which can lead to excessive deformation and pavement rutting under traffic loads [14]. Therefore, both fine and coarse aggregates should be made from crushed, tough, and durable stones with angular shapes for better resistance of loads.

Figure 4

Aggregate gradation for an asphalt mix plays a critical role in determining the mixture's properties. Selecting the appropriate gradation is necessary to produce a dense-graded asphalt mixture. Proper gradation ensures a workable mixture that can be easily produced and placed. Additionally, well-graded aggregates guarantee better interlocking and internal friction between particles, which improves resistance to rutting and pavement deformation. On the other hand, aggregate gradation should consider void requirements. Adequate voids between aggregates are essential for allowing the asphalt binder to coat the particles effectively. Furthermore, voids in the asphalt mixture are important to accommodate the thermal expansion of the asphalt within the mix.

Figure 5

Aggregate gradation can be selected based on local specification requirements. Typically, local specifications provide acceptable gradation

ranges for different asphaltic courses. In the absence of local specifications, engineers can refer to international standards, such as ASTM-D3515, which offers various options for aggregate gradation (as shown in Table No: 5).

Table 5

Sieve Size	D-1	D-2	D-3	D-4	D-5	D-6	D-7
	50 mm (2 in.)	37.5 mm (1½ in.)	25.0 mm (1 in.)	19.0 mm (¾ in.)	12.5 mm (½ in.)	9.5 mm (¾ in.)	4.75 mm (No. 4) (Sand Asphalt)
Grading of Total Aggregate (Coarse Plus Fine, Plus Filler if Required) Amounts Finer Than Each Laboratory Sieve (Square Opening), Weight %							
63-mm (2½ in.)	100	---	---	---	---	---	---
50-mm (2 in.)	90 to 100	100	---	---	---	---	---
37.5-mm (1½ in.)	---	90 to 100	100	---	---	---	---
25.0-mm (1 in.)	60 to 80	---	90 to 100	100	---	---	---
19.0-mm (¾ in.)	---	56 to 80	---	90 to 100	100	---	---
12.5-mm (½ in.)	35 to 65	---	56 to 80	---	90 to 100	100	---
9.5-mm (¾ in.)	---	---	---	56 to 80	---	90 to 100	100
4.75-mm (No. 4)	17 to 47	23 to 53	29 to 59	35 to 65	44 to 74	55 to 85	80 to 100
2.36-mm (No. 8) ^a	10 to 36	15 to 41	19 to 45	23 to 49	28 to 58	32 to 67	65 to 100
1.18-mm (No. 16)	---	---	---	---	---	---	40 to 80
600-µm (No. 30)	---	---	---	---	---	---	25 to 65
300-µm (No. 50)	3 to 15	4 to 16	5 to 17	5 to 19	5 to 21	7 to 23	7 to 40
150-µm (No. 100)	---	---	---	---	---	---	3 to 20
75-µm (No. 200) ^b	0 to 5	0 to 6	1 to 7	2 to 8	2 to 10	2 to 10	2 to 10

The FHWA 0.45 power gradation chart is another tool used to determine and verify the gradation of an asphalt mix [28]. In general, the 0.45 power chart, introduced by the FHWA, is convenient for evaluating maximum density. In this chart, the sieve size is raised to the power of 0.45 on the horizontal axis, while the vertical axis represents the percentage passing. The maximum density line for a given aggregate mixture is represented as a straight line from the origin (0,0) to the point of maximum aggregate size (100% passing sieve). The gradation curve for the aggregate in an asphalt mixture is then drawn and compared with the maximum density line. It is important that the gradation curve does not lie exactly on the maximum density line, as this ensures sufficient voids in the asphalt mixture.

Figure 6

Similarly, as with aggregates used for subbase and aggregate base courses, various tests are conducted to verify the soundness, toughness, and quality of the aggregates. These tests include the soundness test, Los Angeles abrasion test, sand equivalency test, flakiness index, elongation index, and others. Table No: 06 summarizes the necessary tests required to assess the quality of aggregates for an asphalt mix.

Table 6

Test	Aggregate type	Requirement
Sieve analysis	Fine aggregate	As per specification
Sand equivalency		≥55%
Soundness (sodium sulfate)		≤10%
Soundness (magnesium sulfate)	Coarse aggregate	≤12%
Flakiness		≤30%
Sieve analysis		As per specification
Soundness (sodium sulfate)		≤10%
Los Angeles abrasion		≤40%
Plasticity index		Non plastic
Water absorption		2%

3.4.2.2 Filler material

Mineral filler may be used to address any deficiency in the combined aggregate for material passing sieve No. 200. The use of mineral filler produces a dense asphalt mixture. Additionally, mineral filler improves the mixture's cohesion, stiffness, density, and stability. Various materials, such as limestone and cement, can be used as filler. The mineral filler must comply with ASTM D242.

3.4.2.3 Asphalt binder

The asphalt binder acts as a bonding agent in asphalt mixtures. It coats the aggregates and fills part of the voids in the aggregate structure,

resulting in a strong bond between the aggregates. Asphalt binder is a sticky, viscous material extracted from crude petroleum. Various methods, such as penetration and viscosity testing, are used to classify different asphalt binder grades. Asphalt binders with lower penetration grades are typically selected for warm climates, while higher penetration grades are used in cold areas.

It is essential to test asphalt binder thoroughly to verify its properties and quality. Various tests are conducted to ensure compliance with specifications, including:

- **Penetration Test:** The penetration test measures the consistency or hardness of the asphalt binder. This test is crucial for classifying and verifying the asphalt binder grade.
- **Flash Point Test:** The flash point test assesses the flammability of the asphalt binder. During this test, the asphalt binder is heated, and a flame is periodically introduced to determine the temperature at which it releases sufficient fumes to ignite. The flash point is also used to detect contamination in the asphalt binder, as contaminants can alter the flash point.
- **Ductility Test:** The ductility test evaluates the flexibility and elasticity of the asphalt binder. It measures the maximum distance the binder can stretch before breaking when pulled at a consistent rate of 50 mm/min [8].
- **Kinematic Viscosity Test:** Kinematic viscosity measures the time required for a fixed volume of asphalt binder to flow through a calibrated capillary viscometer under the influence of gravity. This test evaluates the flow characteristics of the asphalt binder, determining how it will behave during mixing and under specific temperatures. It also assesses the binder's ability to coat aggregates and fill voids effectively.

- **Softening Point (Ring & Ball Test):** As a viscoelastic material, bitumen softens and loses viscosity as the temperature increases. The softening point test determines the temperature at which the bitumen softens significantly. For hot climates, a higher softening point is desirable to ensure the bitumen resists softening under service temperatures.
- **Rolling Thin Film Oven Test (RTFOT):** The RTFOT evaluates changes in asphalt binder properties during the mixing and laying processes [5]. In this test, a bitumen sample is heated for 85 minutes while being rotated and exposed to air and heat. The residual sample will approximately mimic the asphalt's behavior and properties in pavement. The test measures the mass loss of the sample and evaluates residual properties such as penetration and ductility to determine the effects of hot-mix asphalt processing on the binder.

3.5 Marshal method of asphalt mix design

The selection of an appropriate asphalt binder grade and verifying its quality through testing alone is insufficient to produce a durable asphalt mix. **Optimum bitumen content (OBC)** is a critical factor that significantly impacts the performance of the asphalt mixture. The bitumen content is influenced by various parameters, including climate, traffic conditions, aggregate properties, and performance requirements.

The Marshall Method of Mix Design is a widely used method for determining the OBC for a given aggregate gradation. In this method, samples are prepared for five different bitumen content, for each bitumen content a set of three specimens are prepared, the samples are prepared using the same aggregate gradation but with varying bitumen content. These specimens are subjected to various tests to evaluate the asphalt mix properties and determine the optimum bitumen content.

- Stability:** Marshall stability is defined as the maximum load a specimen can resist when subjected to a constant rate of deformation loading of 50 mm/min until failure [6]. Specimens should be prepared with identical aggregate gradation, mineral filler, and preparation methods. The maximum load sustained by the specimen is recorded, and corrections may be applied to determine the asphalt mix's stability.
- Flow:** Marshall flow refers to the deformation experienced by the specimen during the stability test. Higher flow values indicate a more flexible and less stiff asphalt mixture. The flow and stability tests are conducted as part of the Marshall design method to thoroughly evaluate the asphalt mixture and determine the OBC. The selected bitumen content must meet specified criteria, including minimum stability/flow values and void requirements.

Figure 7

The second key requirement in the Marshall design method is the voids requirement. The selected bitumen content must ensure that the mixture contains voids within acceptable limits. Mixtures that don't satisfy void requirement will not perform as expected.

- Void in mineral aggregates (VMA)** refers to the voids within a compacted asphalt mix, including both air voids and voids filled with bitumen [14]. Sufficient VMA is essential to accommodate the asphalt binder and ensure proper pavement flexibility to handle thermal stresses. VMA can be determined by the use of the following Equation:

$$VMA = 100 - \frac{Gmb * Ps}{Gsb}$$

Where:

Gmb is bulk specific gravity of a paving mixture

Ps is the percentage of aggregates from the total mix

Gsb is the bulk specific gravity of aggregate

Factors such as aggregate gradation significantly influence VMA, making it a critical consideration during aggregate selection.

- Air voids** represent the percentage of voids in a compacted asphalt mix that are not filled with binder. These voids provide space for thermal expansion and contraction of the pavement. Percentage of air voids in asphalt mixture can be calculated using the following equation:

$$Pa = 100 - \frac{Gmb}{Gmm}$$

Where:

Gmb is bulk specific gravity of paving mixture

Gmm is the maximum specific gravity of a paving mixture

- Void filled with asphalt (VFA)** is the percentage of VMA (Voids in Mineral Aggregates) filled with asphalt binder. This property is crucial as it indicates

how effectively the asphalt binder coats the aggregates and fills the voids. The binder should effectively coat the aggregates and fill the voids to provide bonding between the aggregates and flexibility to the asphalt mixture. VFA can be calculated using the following equation

$$VFA = 100 * \frac{VMA - Pa}{VMA}$$

Low VFA will result in poor bonding between aggregates, which can seriously impact pavement performance. On the other hand, a high VFA is also not preferred, as it can lead to a tender mixture, resulting in excessive pavement deformation and bleeding

Density is an important property that is determined for all road layers to assess the degree and effectiveness of the compaction. It is also determined for Marshall specimens to evaluate the degree of compaction, determine the optimum bitumen content, and measure the voids in the asphalt mixture. The specimens for the Marshall test are compacted using a special compaction hammer. The number of blows applied by the compaction hammer depends on traffic conditions and can be 35, 50, or 75 blows. The number of blows increases with the level of traffic. For example, for heavy traffic roads, the number of blows is 75, indicating greater compaction effort and higher density, while for light traffic roads, the number of blows is 35, meaning the desired density will be lower. The density of Marshall specimen or asphalt cores for completed asphalt course can be determined by immersing the specimen in water to measure its mass in water. The specimen is then removed, blotted with a damp cloth to measure its mass in a surface-dry condition. The difference in masses can be used to determine the volume of the asphalt specimen. The bulk density of asphalt can be calculated using the following equation.

$$\gamma_{bulk} = \frac{A}{B - C} * \gamma_w$$

Where:

A is the dry mass of the specimen in air

B is the mass of saturated surface dry specimen in air

C is the mass of the specimen in water

γ_w is the density of water

The determined density for Marshall specimen will be considered as a reference for the required compaction in the field. Furthermore, the density of the completed asphalt courses will be measured and compared to Marshall density.

Table 7

Marshall Method Criteria ¹	Light Traffic ³ Surface & Base		Medium Traffic ³ Surface & Base		Heavy Traffic ³ Surface & Base	
	Min	Max	Min	Max	Min	Max
Compaction, number of blows each end of specimen	35		50		75	
Stability ² , N (lb.)	3336 (750)	-	5338 (1200)	-	8006 (1800)	-
Flow ^{2,4,5} , 0.25 mm (0.01 in.)	8	18	8	16	8	14
Percent Air Voids ⁷	3	5	3	5	3	5
Percent Voids in Mineral Aggregate (VMA) ⁶	See Table 7.3					
Percent Voids Filled With Asphalt (VFA)	70	80	65	78	65	75

NOTES:

- All criteria, not just stability value alone, must be considered in designing an asphalt paving mix.
- Hot mix asphalt bases that do not meet these criteria when tested at 60°C (140°F) are satisfactory if they meet the criteria when tested at 38°C (100°F) and are placed 100 mm (4 inches) or more below the surface. This recommendation applies only to regions having a range of climatic conditions similar to those prevailing throughout most of the United States. A different lower test temperature may be considered in regions having more extreme climatic conditions.
- Traffic classifications
 Light Traffic conditions resulting in a 20-year Design ESAL < 10⁴
 Medium Traffic conditions resulting in a 20-year Design ESAL between 10⁴ and 10⁶
 Heavy Traffic conditions resulting in a 20-year Design ESAL > 10⁶
- The flow value refers to the point where the load begins to decrease. When an automatic recording device is used, the flow should be corrected as shown in section 7.3.3.3.
- The flow criteria were established for neat asphalts. The flow criteria are often exceeded when polymer-modified or rubber-modified binders are used. Therefore, the upper limit of the flow criteria should be waived when polymer-modified or rubber-modified binders are used.
- Percent voids in the mineral aggregate are to be calculated on the basis of the ASTM bulk specific gravity for the aggregate, as discussed in chapter 5.
- Percent air voids should be targeted at 4 percent. This may be slightly adjusted if needed to meet the other Marshall criteria.

The results of Marshall testing for five different bitumen contents will be represented in a set of Marshall curves, as shown in the figure NO.08. In the figure, we can see the curves for different Marshall properties, such as specimen density, flow, stability, VIM, VFA, and air voids, versus bitumen content. The selected bitumen content should satisfy the Marshall design criteria, as per Table No.07, or satisfy local specifications and requirements.

Figure 8

3.6 Pavement construction and testing

Selecting a suitable asphalt job mix formula and using high-quality materials should be integrated with appropriate pavement construction practices to ensure a high-quality and durable outcome. Pavement construction must adhere to established standards and specifications. The methods employed during construction should be verified by the Engineer to ensure optimal results. The following sections explain various points to consider during pavement construction to produce a durable pavement that complies with standards and specifications.

3.6.1 Pavement construction trial (mockup)

It is recommended to construct a full pavement mockup for the proposed pavement. The constructed mockup should resemble the proposed pavement in terms of design and construction. Moreover, the materials used for constructing the mockup must come from approved sources. A mockup can be highly beneficial, assisting the Engineer in verifying and improving the following aspects:

- **Staff Competency:** The trial pavement provides an opportunity to evaluate the competency of staff, laborers, and equipment operators. It can also be used to enhance their skills and correct any deviations or mistakes made during the construction process.
- **Equipment Efficiency:** The mockup construction can be used to assess the efficiency of the equipment. It will help identify unsuitable or defective equipment. Based on the results, the Engineer may recommend replacing defective or inefficient equipment with suitable alternatives to ensure optimal performance.
- **Degree of Compaction:** The mockup can help in determining the number of rollers required to achieve the desired degree of compaction for each pavement layer. It also provides an opportunity to determine the minimum number of passes necessary to achieve the desired degree of compaction. The findings

from the mockup should be implemented during pavement construction to ensure the required compaction is consistently achieved.

- **Laying Thickness of Pavement**

Layers: It is important to determine the ratio of loose to compacted thickness for the pavement layers. Establishing this ratio is critical for Engineers to ensure that the laid pavement layers do not exceed the allowable thickness. Additionally, it aids in achieving a pavement that complies with the required levels and profile.

3.6.2 constructing of granular pavement layers

The method of constructing pavement granular layers should satisfy the following points:

- **Mixing and Laying of Granular**

Materials: Granular materials should be properly mixed before being laid to avoid segregation. Segregation of materials should be prevented, as it can negatively impact the compaction and reduce the strength and stability of the pavement layers. Any segregated materials must be replaced. Excessive segregation can result from poor mixing or poor laying practices. Figure NO.09 illustrates clear segregation in a granular layer caused by poor mixing and laying practices.

Figure 9

- **Compaction of Granular Layers:** The laid layers must be compacted to the required degree of compaction, which measures the density of granular layers after compaction compared to their maximum dry density. Achieving the desired compaction requires applying lessons learned from the mockup, such as selecting the appropriate type of rollers and applying the number of passes needed. Another critical factor is the moisture content, which should be close to the optimum moisture content. Significant deviations in moisture content can greatly impact the compaction of the laid materials.

Figure 10

- **Layer Thickness:** The thickness of the laid granular layers must remain within the allowable limits. Exceeding the permissible thickness can reduce the effectiveness of compaction and negatively affect the degree of compaction. Thicker-than-permitted layers may fail to achieve the required density. Therefore, the Engineer must ensure that layer thickness remains within the allowable limits or aligns with the findings of the road mockup.
- **Level and Alignment:** It is crucial to ensure that the levels, profile, and alignment of the laid granular materials

comply with the approved drawings. The Engineer must verify that these parameters are within the specified tolerances to maintain pavement quality and performance.

Upon completing the laying and compaction of granular layers, field density tests should be conducted to verify the degree of compaction. Performing these tests at the specified frequency is an essential quality control measure to ensure compliance with the required specifications and standards.

3.6.3 constructing of asphaltic layers

Special attention should be exercised during the construction of asphaltic layers. Constructing asphaltic layers for pavement is more complex compared to granular layers and requires skilled workers and appropriate equipment. The following points should be considered during the construction of asphaltic layers:

- **Prime Coat:** The prime coat is sprayed on the final granular layer before laying the asphalt layer. The purpose of spraying the prime coat is improving adhesion between the granular and asphalt layers, binding loose particles together, and waterproofing the granular layer to prevent moisture penetration into the asphalt layer [9]. The prime coat must be applied at a specific rate and allowed to cure and be absorbed by the granular layer before laying the asphalt. Asphalt should only be laid after the prime coat has fully cured; premature laying may compromise the quality of the asphalt layer.
- **Weather Limitations:** Asphalt should not be laid under adverse weather conditions, such as temperatures below 10°C, rain, dust storms, fog, or other unsuitable conditions. Ignoring these weather limitations can compromise the quality and durability of the pavement.

- **Asphalt Temperature:** Before laying the asphalt mixture, asphalt mixture temperature should be verified. Mixtures that are too hot or too cold should not be used, as this can affect the pavement's quality and durability. For instance: Low-temperature asphalt mixtures are difficult to compact and adhesion between aggregates is significantly reduced. The mixing and compaction temperatures are determined by the relationship between the asphalt binder's temperature and viscosity [14]. Compaction temperature corresponds to a viscosity of 0.17 ± 0.02 Pa·s. while, mixing temperature corresponds to a viscosity of 0.28 ± 0.03 Pa·s [14].

Figure 11

- **Laying of Asphalt:** Asphalt is laid using pavers. Prior to laying, the pavers and other equipment must be inspected to ensure they are in proper working condition. Laying should be continuous and without disruption. Sufficient paving machines must be available to cover the entire road width. For wide roads, a sufficient number of pavers should be used to cover the full road width. Using a single paver to lay asphalt on wide roads should be prohibited, as it can result in the formation of cold joints in the asphalt layers. The Engineer must verify the

temperature of the laid asphalt at joint locations. If the temperature falls below 80°C, adhesion at the joints will be inadequate, and compaction will fail to achieve the required density. In cases where asphalt laying is interrupted or a paver breaks down, causing the laid asphalt temperature to drop below 80°C at the joint location, the joint must be properly prepared before laying continues. Preparation includes Saw cutting the joint end to create a vertical surface and applying a tack coat to the joint to ensure proper adhesion with the new asphalt layer.

- **Compaction of Asphalt:** Compaction should be performed using suitable equipment to achieve the required density. The equipment, rolling sequence, and number of passes should follow the procedures established during the road trial. Poor compaction leads to reduced density, increased air voids, decreased bearing capacity, and reduced pavement durability.
- **Asphalt Layer Thickness:** The thickness of the asphalt layer should adhere to the approved design. Reduced thickness results in lower structural capacity, severe defects, and decreased pavement durability. On the other side, the maximum layer thickness for a single lift should not exceed specified values (refer to Table NO.08). Laying layers thicker than the maximum allowable thickness will make both laying and compaction difficult.

Table 8

Asphalt course	Compacted thickness
Base course	60-100 mm
Binder course	50-80 mm
Wearing course	40mm-60mm

The Engineer should also consider the loose-compacted thickness ratio.

Generally, the loose thickness of the asphalt layer should be increased by approximately 25% to achieve the required thickness after compaction. However, the exact loose-compacted thickness ratio for asphalt layers can be determined from the road mockup or trial.

For layers exceeding the maximum allowable laying thickness, the asphalt should be laid in multiple lifts to ensure proper compaction and adherence to design requirements. By adhering to these guidelines, the construction of asphaltic layers can achieve the desired quality, durability, and compliance with specifications.

- **Pavement Geometry:** The Engineer must ensure that the constructed pavement conforms to the approved layout and design.
- **Joints:** Joints between asphalt layers are potential weak points. Before laying new asphalt, the joints should be: cut vertically, cleaned thoroughly and sprayed with a tack coat to improve adhesion.

Additionally, the joints of different pavement layers should be staggered, as illustrated in Figure NO.12, to avoid creating a continuous weak plane. Special care must be taken during construction to ensure that joints are compacted sufficiently and meet quality standards.

Figure 12

3.6.4 Testing of pavement during construction stage

It is crucial to verify the constructed works during the construction stage. Various tests are conducted to assess the quality of the work and ensure compliance with specifications and requirements.

3.6.4.1 Testing of subgrade and granular layers

Upon completion of the pavement formation or granular layers (e.g., subbase, aggregate base course), field density tests (FDT) are conducted at various locations to verify the degree of compaction. The degree of compaction is the ratio of field dry density to maximum dry density. Conducting field density tests is essential to control work quality and ensure that the completed work meets the required compaction levels specified in the project documents.

3.6.4.2 Testing of asphalt layers

Completed asphalt layers are also tested to verify various parameters, including compaction, thickness, bitumen content, and aggregate gradation. Testing is performed by collecting loose samples during construction and core samples after completion.

- **Loose Samples:** These are taken for Marshall tests, bitumen content determination, and aggregate gradation analysis.
- **Cores:** Cores are taken from completed asphalt layers to verify layer thickness, degree of compaction, and, if necessary, to determine bitumen content and aggregate gradation.

4.0 Conclusion

Controlling pavement quality requires the implementation of an effective Quality Assurance/Quality Control (QA/QC) system. This system should be comprehensive, covering all aspects related to pavement construction. In

this paper, several factors that impact pavement quality have been summarized:

- **Subgrade:** The designer should thoroughly test the subgrade to ensure its suitability and ability to carry and distribute traffic loads. If the subgrade is unsuitable, the Engineer should propose solutions to strengthen it.
- **Climate:** Dominant climate conditions should be considered during both the design and construction of the pavement. For example, the bitumen grade and content in the asphalt mixture should be suitable for the climate of the region.
- **Traffic Loads:** Accurate determination of traffic loads is critical for precise pavement design. Therefore, conducting classified vehicle surveys and axle load surveys is essential for estimating traffic loads.
- **Pavement Materials:** Materials used in pavement construction should undergo thorough testing to verify their properties. Materials should be tested both at the source and in the field to ensure compliance with specifications and requirements. Inadequate testing of materials may result in the use of low-quality materials, which can significantly affect pavement quality, reduce durability, and compromise structural capacity.
- **Marshall Method of Design:** The Marshall method of design, or similar methods, is necessary to determine the optimum bitumen content that satisfies requirements for Marshall stability, flow, and voids. Therefore, the Marshall method should be applied before starting pavement construction to determine the proper composition of the asphalt mixture.
- **Pavement Construction and Testing:** The method of pavement construction

should meet project specifications and standards. Using competent workers with relevant experience and suitable equipment is vital. Poor construction practices, such as insufficient compaction, can lead to serious defects like cracking, settlement, and rutting. Field testing of pavement layers is also critical to verify the quality of completed work.

The implementation of a comprehensive QA/QC system is essential for ensuring pavement quality. The Engineer should consider all factors that can affect the pavement. Ignoring any aspect can lead to a pavement that is less capable of withstanding loads and is more susceptible to premature aging.

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